

Human interaction and impact on herpetofauna-a review

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SUMMARY

Ethno-zoological studies can help in human population assessment influences on local animal species and in the improvement of feasible managing plans. Therefore they are essential to conservancy efforts. The herpetofauna have utilized in medicine, but there is less information regarding of herptiles field and its effect on the species involved. For agricultural development, deforestation has been done for 10,000 years. Due to this several high-quality species of the wild animal and plants are extinct or endangered and various common species executed new habitats in the last periods of 20th century. Human beings are using land of wild animal and lived near or within the terrain of wild animal and builds negative influence on herpetofauna.

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INTRODUCTION

The variety of life in a given place is referred to as biodiversity. Unlike the more specific word species diversity, the term biodiversity was created to emphasise the many distinct types of differences that exist within and among organisms at various levels of organization. It refers to a region's total number of genes, species, and biomes (Roberts, 1997). Amphibians and reptiles are basic components of the Earth's biodiversity because they play vital roles in food chain like herbivores, predators and prey along with terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Khan, 2006). In the world, more than 10000 reptiles (Uetz, 2016) and more than 7000 amphibians species are documented (AmphibiaWeb, 2018). But, in Pakistan, more than 190 reptiles and 24 amphibians species are documented (Khan, 2006; Lal *et al.*, 2019; Haider and Faiz, 2020; Faiz and Farooq, 2021). Amphibians and reptiles are significant bio-indicators (Babar and Kanwal, 2021). They highlight climate change and can be found in a variety of environments all over the world, with the exception of a few remote islands.

ETHNO-HERPETOLOGY

Ethnoherpetology is a division of "ethnozology" that observe the relations among human cultures and reptiles and amphibians. Ethnozological studies can help in human population assessment influences on local fauna and in the improvement of

feasible managing plans. Therefore they are essential to conservancy work (Alves and Souto, 2015; Alves *et al.*, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

The habitat likings of species must be studied to know the diversity (Riem *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016; Kamal and Faiz, 2022). Species prefer somewhat or totally well populous habitats (Bateman and Fleming, 2012; Riem *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016) but few species of animals like better to live near the human populated areas (Saito and Koike, 2013). Several species are adversely effected by human activities; so that some species choose new environment to live (i.e. urban, rural and agriculture); while other species fallen or involved in endangered list (Recher, 1999).

The world is on the verge of the first significant mass extinction in 65 million years (Balmford *et al.*, 2003). Current world extinction rates for fauna and flora are probably up to 1000 times greater than the former rate in the fossil record (Baillie *et al.*, 2004). Vertebrate fauna are deteriorating at extremely high rates (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005). The versatile utilization of animal species i.e. as art tools, as food (Klemens and Thorbjarnarson, 1995), in medicine (Akhtar, 2021; Altaf and Faiz, 2021; Nazir, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021), entertainment, magic (Alves *et al.*, 2012), music, religion and for trade (Enge, 1993; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2020) is acknowledged since prehistoric (Ijaz and Faiz, 2021).

MEDICINAL USES OF HERPETOFAUNA

The herpetofauna have high utilize in medicine (Zainab, 2021; Habib, 2022), but there is no information regarding the degree of this field and its effect on the species involved (Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2020). This has been noted that stroking, petting, and working with animal species like vertebrates are health advantageous rehearses. These practices lower heartbeat and control stroke (Beetz *et al.*, 2012). Animal based products extracted from different animal species are utilized as folk medicines and assessed about 8.7% of the very important chemicals used in modern health care system (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009). Still, animal based products are ignored as compared to plant species (Alves and Rosa, 2005). Because they have enough traditional knowledge of zoo therapies, residents of rural areas are more reliant on animal-based products (Santos-Fita *et al.*, 2009). Animals species both wild and farm are essential to human beings. But wildlife are in risk due to human involvement in nature like prohibited “hunting” for ornament, foodstuff, drugs, urban utilization, desertification, agriculture growth and industrial use (Rômulo *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf *et al.*, 2018).

Reptile’s species are applied in traditional general drugs mostly (Umair *et al.*, 2022). Their function in general practices is interrelated with therapeutic usage as well as inhibition of diseases has been recorded in many social-cultural zones all over the world. Justification from different sources has shown that people mistreated the meat, eggs, oil, blood, bones, skin, shells and different parts of “reptiles and amphibians” to supply food and materials for making ornamental tool and mystical items for long time. Regardless of all these usages, the herpetofauna is still used for cultural and medicinal aims, along with day-today activities (Alves *et al.*, 2012; Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

Herptiles are known as very interesting and most important animal species (Khan, 1999; Alves and Rosa, 2007; Hussain *et al.*, 2015). In a lot of cultures,

different species of herptiles are applied in ethno medicine and folklore to cure diseases (Alves and Rosa, 2007; Rômulo *et al.*, 2012). About “10,450” of reptiles and “7,850” amphibian species have been appeared (Uetz, 2016) worldwide. In Pakistan more than 190 species of reptiles (Khan, 2006) have been known until now. Traditional application of animal species to treat ailments in human and other animals have been reported in Pakistan so far, apart from few reports on ethnozoology or zootherapies (Haider *et al.*, 2017; Hakeem *et al.*, 2017; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017c; Rauf *et al.*, 2017)

TRADITIONAL USES OF HERPETOFAUNA

Some wandering snake attracter tribes are vigorously contributing in loss of reptilian species. They make deals with wild animals, reptiles, and other creatures. They are also called as "sanyasies" and "Tapri-was," and they have posed a danger to Pakistan's natural reptile population. They relentlessly pursue a variety of reptile species such as *Uromastyx hardwickii*, *U. asmusii*, *Varanus bengalensis*, *V. griseus*, *Python molurus*, *Trapelus agilis*, *Spalerosophis diadema* and *Ptyas muscocus* among others, enticing them with high prices in exchange for the fur of these populations. Furthermore, these “reptiles” are in high requirement on marketplaces, and national physicians use them in research to treat a variety of ailments. (Khan, 2006).

Scincid (skink) populations “Ophiomorus”, “Novoeumeces”, “Mabuya”, and “Eurylepis” are in high requirement in marketplaces due to a high price by "hakims." To create a marketable hold, the herptiles species are eviscerated while still alive, desiccated in the sun, and sold at a premium price as "regmahi," a major component in recipes known as potent sex boosters. The fat of several herptiles is supposed to have medicinal properties for a variety of diseases and is widely employed in the development of balms, wiki oil, and “*Uromastyx*” stiff, which is used against male impotency. In Pakistan “*Uromastyx hardwickii*” and “*Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*” are commonly employed in research labs and educational organisations. The majority of reptiles are employed in anatomical and physiological investigations (Khan, 2006; Altaf *et al.*, 2020).

ANTHROPOGENIC IMPACT ON HERPETOFAUNA DIVERSITY

Amphibians and reptiles are mainly focus matter to anthropogenic activities (Adil *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021). However, their commercial value is hardly considered when examining the value of natural means impressions. Amphibians and reptiles are main components of environments assisting as predators and basic food sources for some species. Some reptiles have been considered as core species. Economic loss as a result of herpetofauna elimination is an important step in understanding the significance of reptiles and amphibians and their requirements for valuable reform. Most of the species are commercially very important. Due to lack of information about their masses the commercial values across regions can be difficult for reptiles and amphibians (Gibbons *et al.*, 2000; Davic and Welsh Jr, 2004; Dumont, 2005).

Growth rate of human population was very slow till 1960s. After that growth rate upgraded, now exceeded up to 7 billion. If the speed of human population growth remains persistent than the population in world could reach 9.3 billion in 2050 (Bloom, 2011). The exponential human population growth creates deleterious effect

on the diversity as well as spreading in worldwide. Enlarged human populations need food, habitation and luxury things; to achieve the demands of urbanization, agriculture intensification, industrialization resulting in pollution growth (Bouma and Droogers, 1998).

For agricultural development, deforestation has been done for 10,000 years. Due to this several high-quality species of the wild animal and plants are extinct or endangered and various common species executed new habitats in the last periods of 20th century (Newton, 2004; Purtauf *et al.*, 2005; Stoate *et al.*, 2009). Human beings are using land of wild animal and lived near or within the terrain of wild animal and builds negative influence on herpetofauna (Şekercioğlu *et al.*, 2012).

Humanities benefit directly or indirectly from biodiversity. Its conservation is required to eliminate the threat of extinction. Bold actions should be done to ensure biodiversity conservation and protection. Several anuran species live in Pakistan's several zones, however not all of them have the same topographical range. Threats faced by amphibian fauna vary depending on the species. The biggest risks that the toad and frogs face in Pakistan are rapid urbanization and industrialization. Amphibian breeding habitats are being depleted as a result of the overdevelopment of housing complexes and industrial zones. Wazirabad, Gujranwala, Rawalpindi, Karachi, Faisalabad, Sheikhpura and other major cities in Pakistan have expanded their limits, resulting in a significant loss of amphibian populations. Closing water pools to keep mosquitoes out in order to reduce dengue and malaria has a negative impact on the amphibian population. Drainage discharge carrying hazardous chemicals heaves out into streams and water bodies, which is a major cause of population reduction in many areas of Pakistan near industrial zones. *Musa ornata*, *Fejervarya syhadrensis*, *Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis* and *H. tigerinus* are among the most afflicted anuran species (Khan, 2006). Main threat to amphibian and reptiles especially snakes are folklore (Altaf, 2022).

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